

Machine Learning Methods for Mushroom Classification

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Abstract: In this paper, different methods has been implemented for classification of mushrooms into 'edible' or 'poisonous'. Supervised machine learning algorithms like multinomial Naive bayes, Gaussian Naive bayes, SGD, KNN, Stacking, Logistic regression, Decision tree and Random Forest are used for model development and testing of the data. Accuracy up to 94% has been achieved with six features.

Keywords: KNN, Random Forest, Decision Tree, SGD, Naïve bayes, Logistic Regression, Cross-Validation, Multi-modal distribution, Accuracy, Model, Label Encoder, Standardization, Classification, Supervised.

I Introduction

Mushroom is a type of fungi which is grown in large wet areas. It is an umbrella shaped fruiting body of order 'Agaricales' in the phylum 'Basidiomycota'.

Mushrooms are one of the high demanding which has some medicinal properties. Thailand has appropriate environment for plant mushroom to be agriculture economy. In 1975 after Karn Cholwijarn instructor study for developing of Infected Mushroom Loaf for making high productivity to export to foreign country [3]. Currently mushrooms that are necessary for agriculture economy in Thailand have 7 type are Straw mushroom, Black mushroom, Champion, Dried Chinese mushroom, Oyster mushroom, Angel mushroom, and Abler mushroom [4].

Commercially important, edible mushrooms include *portobellos* (*Agaricus bisporus*), whose forms include button mushrooms, cremini, and baby bellas, and shiitake (*Lentinula edodes*). The morels (*Morchella*, *Verpa*) and false morels or lorchels (*Gyromitra*, *Helvella*) are popularly included with the true mushrooms because of their shape and fleshy structure; they resemble a deeply folded or pitted conelike sponge at the top of a hollow stem. Some are among the most highly prized edible fungi (e.g., *Morchella esculenta*). Edible truffles (various *Tuber* species), which hardly resemble mushrooms, are also popularly labelled as

such. These and other edible mushrooms and fungi are free of cholesterol and contain small amounts of essential amino acids and B vitamins. However, their chief worth is as a specialty food of delicate, subtle flavour and agreeable texture. By fresh weight, the common commercially grown mushroom is more than 90 percent water, less than 3 percent protein, less than 5 percent carbohydrate, less than 1 percent fat, and about 1 percent mineral salts and vitamins.

Poisoning by wild mushrooms is common and may be fatal or produce merely mild gastrointestinal disturbance or slight allergic reaction. It is important that every mushroom intended for eating be accurately identified.

This paper focuses on creating a model to detect poisonous or edible mushroom which will distinguished based on it's features like shape, surface, colour, odor etc. this classifies whether the mushroom is eatable or not.

II Methodology

In this research we used following steps:

i. Data Collection

The dataset has been taken from Kaggle ([Mushroom Classification](#)). It consists of 23 features like class, cap-shape, cap-surface, cap-colour, bruise, odor gill-attachment, gill-spacing, gill-size, gill-color, stalk-shape, stalk-root, stalk-surface-above-ring, stalk-surface-below-ring, stalk-color-above-ring, stalk-color-below-ring, veil-type, veil-color, ring-number, ring-type, spore-print-color, population, habitat. It has 8124 records. Class has two values of p (Poisonous) and e (Edible).

ii. Data preparation

In this dataset there is no any null values. Then applied label encoder to convert categorical data into numeric data.

Table 1: Dataset after applying Label Encoding

class	Cap-shape	Cap-surface	Cap-color	∴	population	habitat
1	5	2	4	.	3	5
0	5	2	9	.	2	1
0	0	2	8	.	2	3
1	5	3	8	.	3	5
.
0	5	2	4	.	1	2

Standardization method has been used to scale the data. Then removed veil-type feature as it contains all the value as 0.

iii. Visualization

Checked for correlation between the data by plotting heatmap and found there is a strong correlation between gill-attachment and veil-color of value 9.

Then plotted distribution graph to check the value distribution and with respect to class. All feature are in multi-modal distribution which can contribute for our model.

iv. Feature Selection

Wrapper method has been used for feature selection [5] where it gives 6 features such as 'cap-shape', 'gill-attachment', 'gill-spacing', 'gill-size', 'stalk-shape' and 'stalk-surface-above-ring'. Logistic regression is used for feature selection in wrapper method.

$$\sigma(z)=1/1+e^{-z}$$

v. Model Development

In development of model, used various algorithms of all classes such as linear, non-linear, local and generative.

- Random Forest

It will construct the multiple decision trees and decides based on the voting of each decision trees. It uses bagging method to build multiple decision trees and combines the output for the better result.

- Stacking classifier

This will uses multiple models for the better prediction. It uses **meta-model** to learn how to best combine the predictions of base models.

- K-Nearest Neighbour

It predicts the new data point by looking at the 'K' closest point. It chooses K points and calculates the distance between each points for new data points. Arrange them in increasing order. Then finds the nearest neighbours and decides based on majority voting.

Euclidean Distance formula is used to calculate the distance.

$$d=\sum_{i=1}^n(x_{2i}-x_{1i})^2$$

- Naïve Bayes Multinomial

It assumes all the features as independent of each other. It classifies based on the frequency.

To calculate the probability of a message belonging to a certain category Multinomial Naive Bayes uses the multinomial distribution:

$$P(X) = \frac{n!}{n_1!n_2!\dots n_m!} p_1^{n_1} p_2^{n_2} \dots p_m^{n_m}$$

- Logistic regression

It uses Sigmoid function to map the data between 0 and 1.

$$\sigma(z) = 1 / (1 + e^{-z})$$

First it calculates the linear combination of all the features

$$z = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i \right) + b$$

then applies the sigmoid function to it. Then classifies the input as 0 or 1 based on threshold value usually as 0.5.

$$P(y=1) = \sigma(z)$$

$$P(y=0) = 1 - \sigma(z)$$

It uses Gradient descent to calculate the loss function.

- SGD

In this algorithm it gradually minimizes the error by adjusting the parameter like weight. It considers small dataset instead of considering all data points like gradient descent. It will repeat the process until it gets the minimum error. Advantage of SGD over GD is its computation power is more with large number of data.

- Decision Tree

It is like a flowchart where it consists of root, internal node and leaf node. In every step it classifies based on each feature. Branches will have Yes/No. The depth of decision tree also can be decided for best result to avoid overfitting.

Different methods are used for training and testing.

- Train-test-split

Here 50% of data is used for training and 50% is used for testing. And applied the algorithms such as Naïve bayes multinomial, Gaussian naïve bayes, KNN, SGD and Stacking classifier [1].

- Cross validation

10 fold cross validation is used for training and testing of data[2] and applied algorithms such as Naïve bayes multinomial, Gaussian naïve bayes, KNN, SGD and Stacking classifier, Logistic regression, Decision tree and Random forest.

vi. Model Evaluation

Accuracy, Recall, Precision, F1-Score are used for evaluating model.

Accuracy:

Accuracy represents the number of correctly classified data instances over the total number of data instances.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TN + TP}{TN + FP + TP + FN}$$

Precision:

Precision should ideally be 1 (high) for a good classifier. *Precision* becomes 1 only when the numerator and denominator are equal i.e $TP = TP + FP$, this also means FP is zero. As FP increases the value of denominator becomes greater than the numerator and *precision* value decreases.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

Recall:

Recall should ideally be 1 (high) for a good classifier. *Recall* becomes 1 only when the numerator and denominator are equal i.e $TP = TP + FN$, this also means FN is zero. As FN increases the value of denominator becomes greater than the numerator and *recall* value decreases.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

III Results

In this experiment, we divided the data into 50% training and 50% testing. It gives the result as follows:

Table 2: Accuracy results for 50 training and 50 Testing

Multinomial NB	79.99%
Gaussian NB	93.05%

SGD	96.45%
KNN	99.68%
Stacking	100%

Table 3: Classification report for Stacking method with 50 training and 50 testing

Stacking Classifier Accuracy: 1.0

Classification Report:				
	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1257
1	1.00	1.00	1.00	1181
accuracy			1.00	2438
macro avg	1.00	1.00	1.00	2438
weighted avg	1.00	1.00	1.00	2438

As an other experiment, we took 10-fold cross validation for training and testing. It gives the result as follow:

Table 4: Accuracy results for 10-fold CV method

Multinomial NB	75.76%
Gaussian NB	84.64%
SGD	88.49%
KNN	95.02%
Stacking	93.28%
Logistic regression	95.69%
Decision tree	96.11%
Random forest	96.57%

In this experiment, we got 96.57% mean accuracy in random forest. In this n_estimator is considered as 150 for the better prediction.

Table 5: Classification report of Random Forest with 10-fold CV

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Random Forest - 10-Fold Cross-Validation Accuracy Scores:
[0.68511685 1. 1. 1. 1. 1.
 1. 1. 0.97167488 1. ]

Mean Accuracy: 0.9657
Standard Deviation: 0.0939

=== Random Forest - Classification Report (10-Fold CV) ===
      precision    recall  f1-score   support

   Edible         0.94      0.99      0.97      4208
  Poisonous       0.99      0.93      0.96      3916

   accuracy
  macro avg         0.97      0.96      0.97      8124
  weighted avg         0.97      0.97      0.97      8124

```

In this experiment, we are getting 100% accuracy with Stacking model. In stacking model, Random forest and SVC are considered as a base learner and Logistic regression as a meta learner.

As an other experiment, Wrapper feature selection method has been applied for selection of features where 6 features has been taken then applied 10-fold cross validation method to the selected features. And the results are as follows:

Table 6: Accuracy results for wrapper feature selection method with 10-fold CV

Multinomial NB	77.86%
Gaussian NB	64.01%
SGD	93.80%
KNN	92.96%
Logistic Regression	93.89%
Decision Tree	94.18%
Random Forest	94.18%
Stacking Classifier	93.67%

In in this experiment, we are able to 94.18% accuracy with decision tree and Random forest.

After conducting different experiments which are by splitting, cross validation for all features and cross validation for selected features, we compared the accuracy of different models with splitting and cross validation. Even though splitting is giving more accuracy with 100% in stacking, cross validation is giving 93.28% with all features and 94.18% with selected features, which means with splitting as it uses part for training and testing, it may cause some bias. Also it is a sign of overfitting of the model which is not acceptable. In cross validation, it covers all pattern in the data as it takes parts of data and do both training and testing. With only 6 features, we could be able to achieve accuracy of 94.18%, which is the best compared to considering all 22 features and getting 2% more accuracy. So with this experiment we will consider Random Forest and decision tree model with accuracy level of 94.18% as the best with wrapper method feature selection.

Conclusion:

In our work, focused on building a better model with less bias and better accuracy model with minimum features. It classifies mushroom class into 'edible' or 'poisonous'. The dataset from Kaggle has been taken and reached up to mean accuracy of 94.18% accuracy in Random Forest model. Other than accuracy we checked for Precision, Recall, F1-Score and support.

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